

TOWARDS OPEN SEARCH APPLICATIONS FOR THE BROADER COMMUNITY

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Abstract

In recent years, a handful of commercial search providers dominated the world's search ecosystem and, to a large extent, the world's information flow. Over the years, many open issues relating to such a dominating ecosystem have been identified, and multiple tools and user groups were created in an attempt to address these issues. As part of the Open Search Foundation's Applications Working Group, we aim to explore open-search-based applications which could address the identified issues. To that end, this paper aims to identify privacy issues connected to the reliance on a few commercialised search solutions, potential data sources which could be used to enhance an open search index, as well as app ideas for enhancing and leveraging an open search index. A first pilot study was performed with two diverse student groups to get an insight into user requirements related to open search.

The findings indicate that students with substantial technical knowledge see search result and market manipulation as the main issues. In contrast, students with less technical knowledge see ads and recommended content as issues. Furthermore, many data sources for an open index have been identified. Finally, a multitude of apps for extending as well as using an open search index was identified. These insights can be used to conduct further studies and guide the development process of new independent apps based on an open search index concept.

INTRODUCTION

Soon after its invention, the WWW transformed into a universal information system for the broader community enabling data and information creation and sharing but also collaboration and social networking. From its early days on, the nature of the WWW required tools for searching resources and content. Thus, different types of search systems and services emerged, which can be classified as catalog-based, crawler-based, and meta-search-based systems [1–3].

A significant number of search tools and initiatives emerged, however over the years, by vertical integration, consolidation and concentration, only a few big players are still on the market and offer their services [4–6]. Users, businesses, NGOs and even governments increasingly rely on these few services and depend on access to relevant search results to satisfy their information needs but also stay visible to others [5, 7, 8]. Recent developments in the context

of copyright regulations in Australia between the government and global search and social media companies have shed some light on dominant markets and high dependencies [9]. Access to content and search indices as well as to fair search results have become basic infrastructures such as water, power supply or GPS data for navigation. This recent example may illustrate just the tip of an iceberg as research groups and interest groups in several subject domains have uncovered various problems over the last years. Issues include aspects such as restricted accessibility; privacy, security, and trust; bias, information asymmetries as well as data-driven discrimination and differentiation [10–14].

Several tools and services have been initiated to overcome at least partially the above-outlined issues. These cover a wide range of features from privacy-preserving access to search services to alternative and domain-focused search to an open search index (OSI). This trend is also reflected by diverse user groups who want to get their information needs served apart from mainstream services in a transparent and unbiased way [13, 15–17]. In particular, the latter motivated us to initiate the Applications Working Group within the Open Search Foundation (OSF) [17, 18] and to explore open-search-based apps for the broader community.

This research aims to identify possible applications based on an OSI for the broader community by following the Design Science Research (DSR) approach. This paper focuses on student user groups in different subject domains to uncover their needs, extract possible features for search apps and ideas for apps built on the OSI. To this end, the remainder of this paper is organized as follows: section 2 covers background and related work, section 3 outlines the study design, which is followed by findings and discussion in section 4. Finally, section 5 introduces a first app idea based on the findings which will be implemented as a sample app within the OSF community. The main contribution of this work is the identification of multiple user needs in the context of an OSI, multiple groups of features for an open search app and various app categories which could be built on an OSI. These insights can guide future developments of open search indices and the apps using them.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Time Berners-Lee's first proposal of the World Wide Web (W3 or WWW) in 1989 has adoption soon by the research community, and become a global and widely used information and collaboration space in many application domains [19, 20]. Due to the concept and architecture de-

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sign, a flexible and scalable space for information and data publishers and consumers has been created. However, the decentralized architecture of the W3 implementation also yielded issues such as broken hyperlinks between resources and opened new questions such as how to effectively index and search for resources [21].

Right after the usage of the WWW by geographically dispersed user groups, the first search services and tools appeared already around 1993. One of the first was a manually compiled and managed central index of Web resources for browsing, also followed by distributed ones and enhanced with search features, which have become known as search catalogs [1, 4]. Already in the same year, the first web crawler, originally for Web statistics, appeared. Soon after, it was used to build an automatically compiled search index, first based on a few metadata and gradually enhanced towards a full-text search and is also known as crawler-based search engine [1, 2, 4]. Unlike the first central indexes, distributed crawler-based search engines appeared in the mid to late 1990s. This search architecture allows to split organizational and computational effort, and geographically or subject-based crawling of portions of the Web were possible. In the same way, distributed indices - also geographically and/or subject-based - could be built from one or several crawler instances, and even other indices could be used. Finally, lightweight and rich user clients and interfaces can serve the users according to their needs and end-devices [22, 23]. This conceptual design of a distributed search system has also inspired us to define a conceptual architecture for researching search applications for the broader community.

Soon after the first availability of crawler-based search engines, systems appeared, making use of more than one search engine to increase the coverage of the Web index and provide a unified user interface for the clients. This type of search service has become known as a metasearch system [24–26]. Finally, search systems used by individual users indexing defined parts of the Web and local resources, have been phrased as desktop search [27].

As the Web has developed from a mainly passive consumer-based information system into an active “prosumer” (producer and consumer) one over the last two decades [20], information and communication as well as collaboration habits have changed [28, 29], new features, apps and expectations from different stakeholders have evolved and further are on the horizon.

From a business and start-up viewpoint, in addition to the main search providers, such as Google and Bing, multiple new providers were created, such as Ecosia, DuckDuckGo, Qwant, Chatnoir and more. These alternatives are mainly targeting niches on geographic and content focus as well as privacy protection. However, most of these cannot compete with the largest providers either because of a lack of funding or simply because most popular pages do not allow them to crawl their content [18].

Interest groups, NGOs and policy makers such as the European Union are focusing mainly on security (e.g. exclude

harmful content) and privacy (e.g. protection of private data and behavior, right to forget) as well as unbiased information access and the support of minorities [10, 14, 30, 31]. The OSF campaigns for an open and distributed search index, unrestricted accessible and protecting privacy aspects [18].

Research communities in the field of Information Retrieval (IR) but also in related fields have recently emphasized search features, methods and technologies for the next level of retrieval and web search systems, and suggested possible applications direction for the future. The research communities have identified many features in this context: conversational information seeking; support of complex and long-term information seeking; complement of search result pages by generated information objects; personalized IR but also access to personalized information; incorporating the IoT world in the retrieval process; learnable IR optimizing feature and indexing structure as well as relevance function; new and distributed IR architectures trust concepts; explainability of selection criteria and results. As additional non-functional aspects have fairness, accountability, confidentiality and transparency gained increasing attention [11, 32, 33]. Identified and suggested apps include new ways of web search including domain specific and personalized search; information discovery in social networks, medical search, and e-commerce; conversational information seeking system; personal information systems, notifications and push system; bibliometric and scientific content search; investigative journalism and learning activities [11, 32–34].

Advances in NLP, AI and IR as well as in hardware and software aspect have paved the way to innovative and future-oriented features for research and developing new and enhanced retrieval systems. Therefore new and supportive applications for various user groups are feasible in near to mid-term future. Although search applications and the application of new search features are covered in research, to our best knowledge less has been reported on the needs of the end users and the broader community. Therefore, we want to contribute with our research in gaining better insight in the needs of various user groups. In this paper, we report about our initial step of research and findings by a first selected user group.

STUDY DESIGN

DSR is applied as part of this work to develop apps based on an OSI for the broader community. DSR typically involves creating an artefact - in our case, apps based on an OSI - and/or design theory - in our case, design principles for apps based on an OSI - to enhance and optimise the current state of practice and existing research knowledge. To identify the user needs, be able to make statements about the relevance of (envisioned or developed) apps and perform "good" DSR [35], collective case studies are performed by conducting surveys [36]. Along these lines, two cases are presented in the following.

To investigate how students view privacy issues connected to search posed by large search monopolies, investigate how

they would approach such issues and identify potential solutions which could be developed in the context of the OSF and based on the previously mentioned goal of developing apps based on an OSI for the broader community this paper aims to answer the research questions in Table 1. To answer these questions we surveyed one student group and led a discussion session with another smaller student group and later analysed their responses.

Table 1: Research questions

R1	How do university students view privacy issues of commercial search providers?
R2	What are the data sources students would use for an open search index?
R3	What applications would students like to see developed as part of an open search index?

Settings and Instruments

The students were provided with a document that contained the following items:

- Brief introduction describing how most people and communities are dependent on a few search services
- Description of a conceptual architecture of an open search index seen in Fig. 1.
- Five tasks requiring the student to discuss:
 - Issues of depending on a few search providers
 - Identifying five or more sources that could be used to extend the open search index data
 - Identifying five or more applications that extend the search index data
 - Identifying five or more applications that use the indexed data to provide services
 - Details of two example applications they provided
- A template file with marked sections for each answer, which enables an easier analysis of students answers.

The architecture in Fig. 1 depicts an OSI (3) which is primarily built using data from public web content (1) and data from dynamic content services (2). Data source centred apps serve as an additional source of data that enriches existing index data or provides additional data. The index data can be retrieved either using the open search service or through additional retrieval centred apps that would use the data to provide additional services which are not directly related to search.

Study Participants

The first student group called the *ISR Group* was recruited from an Information Search and Retrieval course at the Graz University of Technology and included 48 students. These

Figure 1: Simplified conceptual architecture of the OSI.

were mainly Masters students focusing on computer science. Additionally this group completed the tasks online, unobserved and without any supervision or input from a lecturer. The second group called the *TET Group* consisted of 6 students and was recruited from the University College of Teacher Education Tyrol. These students focus on primary school education with a focus on mathematics. Furthermore, this group was guided by a lecturer online.

Data Collection and Cleaning

During data cleaning and analysis it was noticed that some students misunderstood questions. These answers had to be removed. Additionally some of the answers contained suggestions which are an essential part of any search app and were therefore left out.

ISR GROUP - STUDY RESULTS

Reliance on a Few Search Providers

We first identify multiple *issues of depending on a few search providers* which we divided and summarized into three groups based on their focus.

Search result influence can shape peoples' opinions by hiding information and changing the rank of web pages. Since commercial companies usually provide search engines, they tend to focus on profit and could therefore influence the results to benefit them financially but would not benefit users. Furthermore, they might influence search results to gain political power, potentially enabling them to gain more profits. On the other hand, authoritarian regimes might force companies to adapt their search results without the users' knowledge. Since commercial providers do not share their algorithms, they are essentially black boxes, making it hard or impossible for users to realise when censoring or the data manipulations mentioned above occur.

The **market influence** group focuses primarily on the interactions between commercial search providers and other companies. Since most of the world relies only on four primary search engine providers, they dominate the market and therefore influence the regulations and their services to suit them best. Furthermore, they enable other companies to advertise in their search results. This creates an environment favouring large established companies with more money and penalising smaller companies.

Some of the issues do not fit in the above groups and are therefore listed here. Firstly, commercial search providers tend to provide their services for free and collect large amounts of personal data in exchange. Because of the above-mentioned lack of transparency, collected data can be used to influence users' opinions or sell their data for profit without the users' knowledge. Additionally, commercial search providers own large server farms, which have a negative environmental impact. Finally, due to market dominance, most people and companies rely on these commercial services to do their tasks. In case one of these services stops operating or blocks, certain entities it could disrupt the entity's source of income.

Data Sources for Extending the OSI

To identify *what data sources could be used to extend the OSI data* we grouped students' suggestions based on the source type. Sources are firstly split into digital and physical resources. The physical resources include maps, books and old church archives. The digital resources are further split into private and public sources.

Private digital sources represent data accessible only by authenticated individuals. They are split into local data located and generated by a personal device and global data located on a protected server, a company's intranet, or even on the OSI. Examples of local sources include user device data, smart device health data and more. On the other hand, examples of global sources include search queries, indexed user data, private social content, a company's intranet, and more.

Public digital sources describe data publicly accessible either by crawling the Web or using an API. These sources are further split into multiple sub-groups. *Verified* sources from official institutions or individuals such as research data, statistics about a country, health data and more. *Social* sources generated through online social interactions such as user relations, social media posts, mailing list content, newsgroup content, question answering sites such as Quora¹, expert input and more. *Document* sources usually stored in larger groups on dedicated servers that may include academic documents, books and more. *Dataset* sources which are either hosted or accessible using APIs and usually contain aggregated data about a specific topic include AWS open data², google public datasets³ and other publicly accessible

datasets. *Media* sources such as images, video, audio content and content related to them such as subtitles, location data and more. *Device* sources generated by publicly accessible devices such as ticket machines, cameras, satellites, public IoT devices and others. *Geographic* sources which usually describe some geographic or traffic aspect include location data, land, water or air traffic data and more. *Other* sources which do not belong into any of the categories mentioned above include user interactions, online wikis, archived content, online retailer content, public data about individuals, code repositories and more.

Applications for Extending the OSI

Next, we investigate suggestions for applications that could *help extend the OSI with new content*. We categorise students' suggestions into two main groups.

Apps requiring user input are represented by two sub-groups. First, apps analysing existing content, such as generating user profiles, web page statistics, and user location tracking. Second, apps that collect user content such as web page reviews, self-reported health symptoms, submission of business opening hours, submissions of research data, and more.

Apps processing existing data generate new content from indexed data. They are split into three sub-groups.

Content analysis apps, analyse existing content to provide new insights such as plagiarism identification, information credibility estimation, content license information and more. Furthermore, these apps also focus on calculating the number of ads and tracking scripts, analysing inter-page interactions by investigating how a topic spreads among pages and analysing the similarity between pages. Finally, these apps also focus on media content by, for example, comparing similarities between videos.

Content generation apps generate content from existing data by adding descriptions and metadata to documents, detecting text and objects in images, summarising content or extracting statistics from datasets or financial data.

Content modification apps generate content by modifying existing data. These apps could, for example, remove bias, automatically translate text or adjust the language level based on the readers' experience.

Applications for Using the OSI

The analysis of *app ideas for using the OSI* resulted in a diverse set of ideas that can be primarily divided into two categories.

Search focused ideas contain ideas for improving the search functionality. It is further divided based on search features and search targets.

Search feature ideas describe suggestions aiming to improve the search experience. These include search execution features such as searching using various input methods and filters, optional search using user preferences, custom-ranking algorithms, and more. Additionally, this group includes ideas for result presentation such as summarization results, filtering results with specific properties such

¹ quora.com

² <https://registry.opendata.aws/>

³ <https://www.google.com/publicdata/directory>

as mobile-friendly pages, presenting connections between different search results and more. Students also suggested multiple ideas for the general search infrastructure such as a search API, self-hosting search indices and browser integration. Finally, general suggestions included the option to delete indexed personal data, support for question answering, optional gathering and analysis of usage data, optional usage of interaction to improve retrieval and more.

Search target ideas focus on search environments, data types and datasets which could be used to perform searches. Suggestions for environments include traditional online searching, offline searching through a local device, searching inside of webpages, inside of documents and search through multiple sources and data types. Data type and dataset suggestions include text documents, media files, sources of a specific document, user reviews, research papers and more.

App focused ideas include suggestions which are not directly associated with search. Just like some of the previous categories this one is divided into multiple sub-categories.

Geo focused ideas primarily encompass features revolving around maps and traffic. Students suggested ideas include an open maps app, navigation app, live visitor data tracking and smart navigation based on crowd movement. Additionally, they also suggested that users should be able to submit their geo data.

Analysis focused apps contain data analysis and monitoring solutions. Idea examples include data visualisation dashboards, trend analysis tools, a data exploration and analysis tool, and more.

Other app idea examples include virtual assistants, government and education-focused apps, news and statement validity estimation apps, business-oriented apps, literature research apps, social networks and many more.

TET GROUP - STUDY RESULTS

Due to the group focus on primary education, tasks were translated into the German language, and some questions had to be left out or reformulated to adjust the survey to the technical understanding of the group. Therefore, only data Sources for extending the OSI and apps for using the OSI were focused.

Data Sources for Extending the OSI

Students suggested including high-quality teaching materials and books such as literature for children. Furthermore, they suggested including more details about the retrieved literature to decide if a product is suitable before buying it.

Applications using the OSI

Students would like to adjust search results using search result filtering, restricting searching to a location and removing ads and networking with, e.g. Facebook. Additionally, they would find it helpful to select the results' language and show the results in their original language (with the optional possibility to translate page afterwards).

This group focused primarily on ads and dynamically recommended content issues. On the other hand, the ISR group mainly focused on privacy-related issues. A lack of technical understanding could explain this difference. It could also further indicate that the wider public should be more informed about tracking and data privacy issues.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper firstly describes the open issues of relying on a few large commercial search providers and introduces open search-based apps. As part of this work, a study is conducted to identify what students view as issues of relying on a few large commercial search providers, what sources they would use to enhance an open index and which open index-based apps they would like to use. A large group of students focusing on IR was surveyed, and a smaller group focusing on teacher education participated in a discussion led by their lecturer. Their answers include issues concerning privacy, dynamic content suggestions and ads. Furthermore, many data sources and data source groups were suggested to enhance an OSI. Finally, multiple app categories that could either enhance an OSI or use it to offer services were identified. The study results can be used to guide further studies and search-based app development.

To broaden the insights of the current study, strengthen our understanding of user needs and identify further issues relating to commercial search giants, we plan on carrying out a study with a more extensive scope in the future. Additionally, as part of the OSF Applications Working Group, we plan on developing an initial prototype based on the insights gathered in this study.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Tom Seymour, Dean Frantsvog, and Satheesh Kumar. History of search engines. *International Journal of Management & Information Systems (IJMIS)*, 15(4):47, sep 2011.
- [2] Saeid Asadi and Hamid R Jamali. Shifts in search engine development: A review of past, present and future trends in research on search engines. *Webology*, 1(2), 2004.
- [3] C. Mic Bowman, Peter B. Danzig, Udi Manber, and Michael F. Schwartz. Scalable internet resource discovery: Research problems and approaches. *Commun. ACM*, 37(8):98–ff., August 1994.
- [4] E. Van Couvering. The history of the internet search engine: Navigational media and the traffic commodity. volume 14, pages 177–206. 2008.
- [5] Patrick Barwise and Leo Watkins. The evolution of digital dominance. *Digital dominance: The power of Google, Amazon, Facebook, and Apple*, pages 21–49, 2018.

- [6] Edward Iacobucci and Francesco Ducci. The google search case in europe: Tying and the single monopoly profit theorem in two-sided markets. *European Journal of Law and Economics*, 47(1):15–42, 2019.
- [7] Shuang Li, Xiang Lan, Yuezhi Zhou, and Yaoxue Zhang. Exploring and understanding web search behavior with human activities. In *2017 IEEE SmartWorld, Ubiquitous Intelligence & Computing, Advanced & Trusted Computed, Scalable Computing & Communications, Cloud & Big Data Computing, Internet of People and Smart City Innovation (SmartWorld/SCALCOM/UIC/ATC/CBDCOM/IOP/SCI)*, pages 1–8. IEEE, 2017.
- [8] Aleksandar Grubor and Olja Jakša. Internet marketing as a business necessity. *Interdisciplinary Description of Complex Systems: INDECS*, 16(2):265–274, 2018.
- [9] Bridget Judd. Google is threatening to pull its search engine from australia. so what does that mean for you? - abc news, 01 2021. <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2021-01-25/google-may-pull-search-engine-from-australia-what-happens-next/13086712>.
- [10] Orla Lynskey. The power of providence: the role of platforms in leveraging the legibility of users to accentuate inequality. pages 177–201, 2018.
- [11] J Shane Culpepper, Fernando Diaz, and Mark D Smucker. Research frontiers in information retrieval: Report from the third strategic workshop on information retrieval in lorne (swirl 2018). In *ACM SIGIR Forum*, volume 52, pages 34–90. ACM New York, NY, USA, 2018.
- [12] Nicholas Diakopoulos, Daniel Trielli, Jennifer Stark, and Sean Mussenden. I vote for—how search informs our choice of candidate. *Digital Dominance: The Power of Google, Amazon, Facebook, and Apple*, 22:320–341, 2018.
- [13] Anas El-Ansari, Abderrahim Beni-Hssane, Mostafa Saadi, and Mohamed El Fissaoui. Papir: privacy-aware personalized information retrieval. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, pages 1–17, 2021.
- [14] Fernando Galindo and Javier Garcia-Marco. Freedom and the internet: empowering citizens and addressing the transparency gap in search engines. *European journal of law and technology*, 8(2):1–18, 2017.
- [15] Wikipedia. List of search engines. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_search_engines, 2021.
- [16] Wikipedia. Outline of search engines. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outline_of_search_engines, 2021.
- [17] OpenSearchFoundation. Open search foundataion official website. <https://opensearchfoundation.org/en/open-search-foundation-home>, 2021.
- [18] Daisuke Wakabayashi. Google dominates thanks to an unrivaled view of the web - the new york times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/12/14/technology/how-google-dominates.html>. (Accessed on 17/06/2021).
- [19] CERN. A short history of the web. <https://home.cern/science/computing/birth-web/short-history-web>, 2021.
- [20] Karwan Jacksi and Shakir M Abass. Development history of the world wide web. *Int. J. Sci. Technol. Res*, 8(9):75–79, 2019.
- [21] Tim Berners-Lee, Robert Cailliau, Jean-François Groff, and Bernd Pollermann. World-wide web: the information universe. *Internet Research*, pages 52–58, January 1992.
- [22] C Mic Bowman, Peter B Danzig, Darren R Hardy, Udi Manber, and Michael F Schwartz. The harvest information discovery and access system. *Computer networks and ISDN Systems*, 28(1-2):119–125, 1995.
- [23] Keith Andrews, Christian Gutl, Josef Moser, Vedran Sabol, and Wilfried Lackner. Search result visualisation with xfind. In *Proceedings Second International Workshop on User Interfaces in Data Intensive Systems. UIDIS 2001*, pages 50–58. IEEE, 2001.
- [24] M Manoj and Jacob Elizabeth. Information retrieval on internet using meta-search engines: A review. *Journal of scientific & industrial research*, 67(10):739–746, 2008.
- [25] Susan Gauch, Guijun Wang, and Mario Gomez. Profusion: Intelligent fusion from multiple, distributed search engines. *Journal of Universal Computer Science*, 2(9):637–649, 1996.
- [26] Erik Selberg and Oren Etzioni. The metacrawler architecture for resource aggregation on the web. *IEEE expert*, 12(1):11–14, 1997.
- [27] Bernard Cole. Search engines tackle the desktop. *Computer*, 38(3):14–17, 2005.
- [28] Harald Weinreich, Hartmut Obendorf, Eelco Herder, and Matthias Mayer. Not quite the average: An empirical study of web use. *ACM Transactions on the Web (TWEB)*, 2(1):1–31, 2008.
- [29] Yupeng Jiang, Yingying Zhao, and Hui Xu. Analysis and portrait of college students’ online behavior habits. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, volume 1302, page 022007. IOP Publishing, 2019.
- [30] Lucas D Introna and Helen Nissenbaum. Shaping the web: Why the politics of search engines matters. *The Information Society*, 16(3), 2006.
- [31] Jahna Otterbacher. Addressing social bias in information retrieval. *Experimental IR Meets Multilinguality, Multimodality, and Interaction*, pages 121–127.
- [32] Iván Cantador, Massimo Melucci, Max Chevalier, and Josiane Mothe. Circle 2020-the first joint conference of the information retrieval communities in europe. In *Joint Conference of the Information Retrieval Communities in Europe (CIRCLE 2020)*, volume 2621, 2020.
- [33] Zhumin Chen, Xueqi Cheng, Shoubin Dong, Zhicheng Dou, Jiafeng Guo, Xuanjing Huang, Yanyan Lan, Chenliang Li, Ru Li, Tie-Yan Liu, et al. Information retrieval: a view from the chinese ir community. *Frontiers of Computer Science*, 15(1):1–15, 2021.
- [34] Yvonne Kammerer, Saskia Brand-Gruwel, and Halszka Jarodzka. The future of learning by searching the web: mobile, social, and multimodal. 6:81–91, 2018.
- [35] Alan R Hevner. A three cycle view of design science research. *Scandinavian journal of information systems*, 19(2):4, 2007.
- [36] Robert K Yin. *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*. Sage publications, 2017.